

IPBES VA Chapter 6 - Constitutions pluralistic value approach text analysis

Code: IPBES_VA_6.1

Versioning: 03 (04.03.2022)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4329704

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Description: This review corresponds to the IPBES Values assessment Chapter 6. The methodology explained in this report refers to the analysis of a Constitutions database to provide insights on the use of plural value approaches within national laws. A text analysis for the Constitutions was designed by identifying the combination of words that provide information towards plural value approaches.

Process overview:

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: Text analysis

Search languages: English

Search Engine: Constitute Project in: <https://www.constituteproject.org/> (Publicly available).

Exact Search Date: 8 April 2020

Sample extracted (A): 202 Constitutions (A)

Location and Format of the Data (A): IPBES_VA_6.1_08-04-2020_(A).csv

Search terms (R1):

```
TS= (
    TITLE-ABS-KEY(
        (
            (world view* OR Weltanschauung OR value* OR pluralistic)
            AND
            (valu* OR participat* OR indigenous)
            AND
            (knowledge OR endemic)
            AND
            (knowledge OR autochthon*)
            AND
            (knowledge OR traditional)
            AND
            (knowledge OR local)
            AND
            (knowledge OR integrat* OR multicriteria OR deliberative)
            AND
            (evaluat* OR multiple knowledge OR noesis OR multiple
            evidence base OR holistic OR trade-off OR tradeoff OR complex OR
            social-ecological OR human environmental OR socio-ecological OR
            human-environmental OR rights of rives OR rights of land OR rights
            to nature OR environmental right* OR instrumental)
            AND
            (valu* OR intrinsic)
            AND
            (valu* OR relational)
            AND
            (valu* OR ecological)
            AND
            (valu* OR environment*)
            AND
            (valu* OR economic*)
            AND
            (valu* OR cultur*)
            AND
            (valu* OR sustainable)
            AND
            (use OR sustainable)
            AND
            (management OR benefit)
            AND
            (sharing OR customary OR wonted)
```

Treatment applied: Application of Search terms to constitutions in (A). The manual used to code the constitutions can be found in (R1).

A + R1 = B

Type of analysis/search/review: Text analysis

Search languages: English

Exact search date: 8 April 2020

Sample extracted (B): 13121 hits (# of times search terms were found by Country Constitution) (B)

- **Fields extracted (B):**

- Country (Country Name),
- Year (the constitution year),
- Order (1 indicates the latest version of the constitution),
- Word,
- Number of occurrence,
- Text (context in which the word is mentioned)

Location and Format of the Data (B): IPBES_VA_6.1_08-04-2020_(B).csv **(B)**

Treatment applied: Identification of context **(R2)** in which the bag of words **(R1)** are found in first search **(B)**.

$B + R2 = C$

Search languages: English

Exact search date: 30 June 2020

Sample extracted (C): 8692 hits (# of times search terms were found by Country Constitution) **(C)**

Fields extracted (C):

- Country (Country Name)Year (the constitution year)
- Order (1 indicates the latest version of the constitution)
- Word_application (the bag of words **(R1)**)
- Word_context (the bag of words we adapted from the Valuation Uptake) **(R2)**
- Text (Cells with the paragraph containing the Word_application and/or Word_context).

Location and Format of the Data (C): IPBES_VA_6.1_30-06-2020_(C).csv

Definition of files

ID	Name	Description of file	File Type
B	IPBES_VA_6.1_08-04-2020_(B).xls	Sample extracted + applied rules of review (R1)	csv
C	IPBES_VA_6.1_30-06-2020_(C).xls	Sample extracted + applied rules of review (R1+R2)	csv
R1	IPBES_VA_6.1_08-04-2020_(A)(R1).csv	Applied rules of review (R1)	csv
R2	IPBES_VA_6.1_08-04-2020_(B)(R2).pdf	Applied rules of review (R2)	PDF